

Forestry - Agriculture interaction

The innovation of maize cultivation between poplar rows

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Maize in a first-year poplar plantation, Santa Fe, Granada.

The cultivation of poplars in the province of Granada offers a series of benefits ranging from the ecological improvement of the environment to the economic and social promotion of the area.

The company Agroservicios Hijo de Celedonio S.L., has incorporated the cultivation of maize into the production of poplars. This practice was already carried out in the past in the area of Vega de Granada, which consisted of growing different horticultural products between the poplar groves rows during the first year of production. Nowadays, the industrialisation of production has led to its disappearance in practically the whole area, but some farmers have recovered it and turned it into a productive strategy.

The cultivation of maize between the poplar rows optimises the use of space and resources, especially soil and water availability. Maize is sown for two seasons.

After these two seasons, the corn crop is rotated to the plot that has been cut that year, so that every two years corn is planted on a different plot of the farm, which consists of a total of 10 plots. From the last corn harvest to the cutting of the wood and depending on the availability of pasture, livestock is used to manage the vegetation cover.

At present there are 125 ha of poplar trees divided into plots of between 10 and 15 ha and each year one of the plots is cut down. Poplar trees, which have a 10-year cycle, are planted at the end of February, while maize is sown in mid-April, taking advantage of the humidity provided by the irrigation that the poplar trees receive at this time. At the same time, maize provides essential ground cover for the development of poplar trees at the beginning of its growth.

The area under the tree that remains unproductive accounts for 30% of the area, however, maize yield in the first year of the poplars is 10,000 kg/ha. In the second year, due to the shade provided by the poplar trees, maize yield is reduced to 6,000 kg/ha. The high profitability of maize allows for increased land use efficiency.

This system ensures that both crops can grow without competing for light and nutrients. As fast-growing trees, poplars provide shade for maize, which helps to reduce soil temperature and evapotranspiration, thus favouring the development of maize during hot summer days.

This farming model allows farmers to diversify their income. While poplars can be harvested every 10 years for timber production, maize can be harvested annually. This provides a steady stream of income and reduces economic risk.

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